

The true 3-D surface reconstruction using a multi-UAV cooperation method

Haigang Sui, Hao Zhang*, Qiming Zhou, Jianya Gong, Yixuan Zhu
State Key Laboratory Information Engineering in Surveying, Mapping and Remote Sensing
Wuhan University
Wuhan, China

* corresponding author: zhanghao.1003@whu.edu.cn

Abstract—Geomorphometry research largely relies on 3-dimensional land surface models, especially for natural landforms with steep slopes and large complex artificial structures. The traditional Digital Elevation Model (DEM) encounters difficulties in representing detailed features in such scenes. To address this issue, this paper introduces a concept of a “true 3D surface” and proposes a multiple Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) collaborative method for high-quality reconstruction of a true 3D surface. We established an evaluation model of scene reconstruction based on the Multi-View Stereo (MVS) modeling rules, and utilized the Fibonacci approach to select the optimal viewpoints. We also adopted the method of finding the next-best-view for each UAV in turn to extend the multi-UAV trajectory. This method involved trade-offs between energy consumption and scene reconstruction to enhance the contribution of viewpoints for improved reconstruction quality of the true 3D surface. Real flight experiments were conducted over the Wuhan University Teaching Building and the Fangshiwan Bridge in Chibi, which revealed a significant improvement in the completeness and precision of the true 3D surface constructed by our proposed method when compared to vertical photography techniques.

I. INTRODUCTION

Building a 3D model of large scenes is essential for a better understanding of terrain and geomorphology, especially when repeated observations and analyses are required. Traditional DEMs are widely used in terrain modeling as they can visually display terrain information of the scene. However, DEMs often struggle to depict detailed facade features of certain natural landforms with large drops, such as the Loess Plateau (Fig. 1a), and large-scale artificial structures, such as tower buildings (Fig. 1b); hence, they do not represent a true 3D surface model.

A true 3D surface goes beyond the visualization of topography in large-scale scenes as it captures sufficient surface details from all angles, including elevations. Compared to traditional DEMs,

true 3D surfaces contain more information and hence provide greater assistance for topography-related research.

(a) Loess plateau

(b) Tower buildings

Figure 1. Natural landforms and artificial features with a large drop

Due to the rapid development of UAV technology, a single high-resolution camera-equipped commercial UAV is now available at a lower cost and has found use in various industries [1-3]. Based on advanced MVS technologies like MVE [4], COLMAP [5], and Pix4D [6], even monocular cameras on UAVs can reconstruct a very detailed true 3D surface.

Several studies have explored the true 3D surface reconstruction of ground surfaces using a single UAV based on the MVS technique [7, 8]. However, most of these studies relied on the traditional vertical photography method, which fails to adequately collect elevation data. As a result, the reconstructed models did not have sufficient elevation details to represent true 3D surfaces. Alternative studies on collecting elevation data by manually-controlled UAVs have shown the drawbacks of being time-consuming, laborious, and challenging to ensure the model's completeness and precision [9].

This paper introduces a multi-UAV collaborative method capable of reconstructing a true 3D surface. Our proposed method

can efficiently devise a collision-free data acquisition path that maximizes scene reconstruction. This allows for autonomous image data acquisition using multiple UAVs which results in a high-quality, precise true 3D surface, based on MVS.

II. METHODS

Our proposed multi-UAV collaborative method consists of three stages. In the first stage, we establish a coarse proxy of the scene through vertical photography and randomly generate sampling points on this proxy. We then employ MVS modeling rules to construct the reconstruction model of the sampling points. In the second stage, multi-UAV trajectories are planned by finding the next-best-view (NBV) in a comprehensive evaluation considering scene reconstruction, flight energy consumption, and distance between the multi-UAV trajectories. By doing so, our method can plan a collision-free data acquisition path that maximizes the scene reconstruction. In the third stage, the UAVs collaboratively capture images autonomously along the planned trajectories, and a high-fidelity true 3D surface is reconstructed through MVS. Figure 2 provides a general summary of our proposed method.

Figure 2. Overview: The first stage: obtain the proxy model and complete the establishment of the reconstruction model. The second stage: multi-UAV extend trajectories in turn. The third stage: multi-UAV collaborative image acquisition, and establish the true 3D surface.

A. Reconstruction Model of 3D Surface

To fully capture the image data of the scene, and reconstruct a fine and complete true 3D surface, we need to avoid planning a wrong trajectory that leads to collision between the UAVs and the ground surface or other obstacles. To achieve this, we can get a coarse proxy of the scene in advance. A DEM can be directly used as the coarse proxy, or we can carry out two-dimensional coverage of the scene by vertical photography of UAV. After that, a coarse proxy of the scene can be quickly established based on MVS.

Given a number of viewpoints $V = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$, we perform Poisson-Disk Sampling on the surface of the coarse proxy to obtain the sampling points $S = \{s_1, s_2, \dots, s_n\}$. According to the

reconstruction rules of MVS, we can establish a reconstruction contribution model of viewpoints v_i, v_j to sampling point s_k , which is shown in Figure 3:

$$c(s_k, v_i, v_j) = w_1(\alpha)w_2(d_1, d_2)\cos(\theta_m) \quad (1)$$

where α is the angle between $\overline{s_k v_i}$ and $\overline{s_k v_j}$, d_1 is the further one of the distances between v_i, v_j and s_k , while d_2 is the other distance. θ_m is the largest of the angles between $\overline{s_k v_i}, \overline{s_k v_j}$ and the normal vector \mathbf{n}_k . In equation (1), w_1 is used to indicate that if the angle between $\overline{s_k v_i}$ and $\overline{s_k v_j}$ is beyond a certain range, the reconstruction will be negatively impacted. w_2 indicates that the reconstruction contribution of the viewpoint to the sample point is negatively related to the distance between them. And $\cos(\theta_m)$ indicates that the greater the angle between the viewpoint and the normal to the plane where the sample point is located, the less significant the reconstruction contribution from the viewpoint. The total reconstruction of the sample point s_k in the viewpoint set V is

$$h_1(s_k, V) = \sum_{\substack{i=1, \dots, |V| \\ j=i+1, \dots, |V|}} \delta(s_k, v_i, \mathbf{p}_i)\delta(s_k, v_j, \mathbf{p}_j)c(s_k, v_i, v_j) \quad (2)$$

where δ is the visibility function of viewpoint v_i to sampling point s_k under direction \mathbf{p}_j . $\delta(s_k, v_i, \mathbf{p}_i) = 0$ when s_k does not exist in v_i 's field of view or the distance between the two is too large; otherwise $\delta(s_k, v_i, \mathbf{p}_i) = 0$.

Figure 3. Reconstruction model of the true 3D surface. The figure shows the profile view when viewpoints v_i, v_j are simultaneously observing the model surface sampling point s_k .

B. Selection of Optimal View Direction

To obtain an accurate true 3D surface reconstruction while also minimizing the number of viewpoints, reducing data acquisition time, and improving the modeling speed, it is essential to ensure that the viewpoints at each position observe in the optimal direction.

The optimal viewing direction is determined by discretizing the viewpoint direction and selecting the direction that maximizes

the reconstruction of the scene. It is critical at this stage to ensure the uniformity of discretization because uneven discretization can create a considerable gap between the chosen and optimal direction.

Initially, we create a sphere of 1 m radius for each viewpoint using the Fibonacci [10] to generate a uniform point set on its surface. A vector set, $P = \{\mathbf{p}_1, \mathbf{p}_2, \dots, \mathbf{p}_M\}$, is formed by computing the vectors from the center of the sphere to each point on its surface, as shown in Figure 4. Here, M represents the total number of vectors. Given a set of viewpoints, $V = \{v_0, v_1, \dots, v_n\}$, we determine the optimal viewing direction for each viewpoint v :

$$\mathbf{p}^* = \arg \max_{\mathbf{p} \in P} h_2(S, V, \mathbf{p}, v) \quad (3)$$

where $h_2(S, V, \mathbf{p}, v)$ is the reconstruction contribution of the viewpoint v to the scene in the direction \mathbf{p} :

$$h_2(S, V, \mathbf{p}, v) = \sum_{\substack{i=1, \dots, |V| \\ k=1, \dots, |S|}} \delta(s_k, v_i, \mathbf{p}_i) \delta(s_k, v, \mathbf{p}) c(s_k, v_i, v) \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{p}_i is the view direction of viewpoint v_i .

Figure 4. Generate uniform discrete point set based on Fibonacci.

C. Cooperative Path Planning of Multi-UAV

The trajectory planning is carried out in a way that multiple UAVs take turns to gradually extend their trajectories from their respective takeoff points.

Firstly, we generate a uniform, high-density collection of candidate viewpoints in the free space of the scene (see Fig. 5). To ensure UAV flight safety, it is vital to maintain a safe distance f between UAVs and surfaces or other obstacles. Furthermore, any candidate viewpoint located in free space, but whose minimum distance to surfaces or obstacles is less than f , is deemed an invalid candidate viewpoint.

Next, each UAV takes turns selecting the NBV, beginning at their respective takeoff points. The method of Wang et al. [11] is utilized to generate a continuous trajectory $L(t)$ (see Fig. 5), where t represents time. The process then repeats by identifying

the NBV and generating a continuous trajectory until the total reconstruction of the scene reaches the target value C .

An evaluation function for the candidate viewpoint v is:

$$H(L, V', S, v) = q_3 H_1(V', S, v) - q_4 H_2(L, V', v) \quad (5)$$

where L denotes the planned continuous trajectory and V' is the set of selected viewpoints. H_1 in Eq. (5) denotes the total contribution of all the viewpoints in V' to the scene reconstruction together with v . H_2 is the incremental energy consumption of the trajectory after adding v as the trajectory end point, which is used to prevent the UAV from consuming too much unnecessary energy, which is detrimental to the reconstruction of the true 3D surface.

Figure 5. The selection of the NBV. The blue point is the candidate viewpoint position, the gray point is the invalid safety viewpoint, the red point is the selected viewpoint, the NBV will be selected from the green point, and the red curve $L(t)$ is the planned trajectory.

The NBV selection method involves extending each UAV a r_1 distance along the tangent direction of the trajectory endpoint. From there, using the KD-Tree nearest neighbor search, all suitable candidate viewpoints within the r_2 distance and not chosen for selection are identified, and the viewpoint maximizing the function H is chosen as the NBV (see Fig. 5).

To ensure safety, we aim to maintain a suitable distance between UAVs during flight. Therefore, we update the evaluation function of the candidate viewpoint v as follows:

$$H(L, V', S, v, s') = H_3(V', v) (q_3 H_1(V', S, v) - q_4 H_2(L, V', v)) \quad (6)$$

$$H_3(V', v) = \begin{cases} 1, & d^* > d_{\min} \\ 0, & d^* \leq d_{\min} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Where d^* is the maximum closest real-time distance from all other trajectories after v has been added to the end of V' and a new trajectory is planned, and d_{\min} is the safe distance between UAVs.

III. RESULT

We conducted real UAV flight and modeling experiments at the teaching building of Wuhan University and the Fangshiwan

Bridge in Chibi. At these locations, we used three DJI Phantom 4 RTKs to cooperatively capture images. The trajectories were planned by our method, and we built a precise 3D surface on the ground using DasEarth software. For comparison, we used the commercial software DJI-Pilot to plan a trajectory for vertical photography, captured images and built a 3D model on the ground using the same method.

Fig. 6 shows the differences in details between the models built using different methods. In the trajectory planned by DJI-Pilot, the direction of all viewpoints is vertical downward, and the distance between the front and rear viewpoints is the same, which makes it difficult to capture the elevation image of the scene. This problem is particularly obvious for the buildings with eaves and bridges with piers. However, our method avoids the above problems by observing the scene from multiple positions and angles.

(a) Teaching building of Wuhan University
 (b) Fangshiwan Bridge in Chibi
 Figure 6. Detailed display of true 3D surfaces. The first row is a panorama, and the second and third rows are a detailed comparison between the method of this paper and the vertical photography method. The left is vertical photography, and the right is the method of this paper.

In the experimental comparison of Wuhan University's teaching building in Figure 6(a), the traditional vertical photography model lacks numerous details under the eaves, while several areas of the model appear distorted, with fuzzy, unrecognizable text on its surface. In contrast, our method retains far more texture under the eaves, and the building's surface text is crystal clear. Comparably, traditional vertical photography in Figure 6(b) not only agglutinates to render a partial pier structure but also loses the texture of the fence surface. Our method, on the other hand, performs remarkably well regarding the comprehensiveness of the bridge piers and the richness of the surface texture.

IV. CONCLUSION

A method for true 3D surface reconstruction using multi-UAV cooperation is proposed in this paper. This method establishes a

mathematical model of scene reconstruction based on MVS, which provides a reasonable evaluation of the contribution of viewpoints to the scene reconstruction. Furthermore, we use the Fibonacci sequence to quickly determine the optimal view direction. Multi-UAV path planning is done using a method where UAVs take turns in finding the NBV and gradually extending the path. Experiments conducted on Wuhan University's teaching building and Fangshiwan Bridge in Chibi demonstrate a marked improvement in the fineness and completeness of the true 3D surface when compared to traditional vertical photography.

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